

MODERNIZATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN

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Looking back at the history of civilization, we can see that in ancient times, our ancestors used various tools to educate and educate the younger generation. Various stones, bones or fruit seeds were used for teaching arithmetic, waxed boards for teaching writing, and a stick with a sharp metal blade attached to the end known as a "stylo". Today, the state education standard, curriculum and textbook are the main tools of English language teaching.

State educational standard. The full name of the document was adopted as "State Education Standard of the Continuous Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan". It specifies the educational content for the A1 level in foreign language and the requirements for the level of preparation of graduates of the A1 level in foreign language.

Competencies in DTS are divided into the following groups (see Figure 1):

Figure 1. The components of communicative competence, the requirements for the level of preparation of graduates of DTS, are taken in relation to the pan-European system of knowledge of foreign languages, and they are presented in a simple and understandable form. Foreign languages

Communicative competence, Sociolinguistic competence, Linguistic competence

Pragmatic competence, Speech competences, Language competencies, Listening comprehension, Speaking, Reading, Graphics and Orthography Phonetic competence Lexical competence. Grammatical competence "I understand and can use commonplace expressions and simple sentences to meet specific needs." I can introduce myself and others, as well as answer and ask questions regarding personal information such as where I live, who I know, and what I own. If the interlocutor speaks clearly and is prepared to help, I can exchange information in a straightforward manner."¹. The Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) is a universally recognized standard that was developed within the framework of the "Language Learning for European Citizenship" program, which was implemented in 1989-1996 in order to ensure transparency, coherence, and consistency in learning and teaching modern languages in Europe, and by a decision of the Council of Europe in 2001, foreign language education in European countries was recommended to be introduced into the system. The CEFR is a fundamental standard. Based on this standard, in the teaching of English in Uzbekistan, the emphasis is not on the student's acquisition of linguistic knowledge, but on the acquisition of speech (communicative) and cultural (intercultural) skills (competencies). - it is recommended to use the cumulative method.

Program. The full title of the document was adopted as "Foreign (English, German, French) language curriculum for general secondary schools". This educational tool includes an introduction, a letter of introduction, the purpose of English language teaching, the content of English language teaching, the requirements for practical English language learning, the

¹ Ўзбекистон Республикасининг Давлат тили ҳақидаги Қонуни. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий Мажлис Ахборотномаси. – №12.– Тошкет, 1995. – 257-модда.

amount of lexical units that students should acquire from English, the minimum of English grammar and pronunciation, and each part of English in general secondary schools. consists of such parts as the distribution of topics studied in the classroom. The teacher executes the program, and the students learn it. Preparation of programs for Uzbek universities has its own history. Until 1968, localized copies of programs designed for Russia were used in Uzbek schools. The program project for Uzbek schools was developed in 1968 and introduced in colleges in the 1970/71 academic year. In 1999, the curriculum was updated and new textbooks were created based on it.

In connection with the introduction of mass learning of a foreign language from the 1st stage of all universities, the State Education Standard for Foreign Languages of the Continuing Education System with reference to some cases of the international document "European Competences for Foreign Language Acquisition: Learning, Teaching, Assessment" (CEFR) of the Council of Europe and Curricula were developed and gradually implemented starting from the 2013–2014 academic year. The specially selected teaching content in accordance with the program is the main educational object in the acquisition of communicative competence in a foreign language. Two aspects are observed in the teaching content: what to learn and what to learn. The first is the learning material and the second is the learning process. Study material takes place in the program. Second, since it is a process of formation of communicative competence related to skills and competences, the corresponding requirements are listed in the program. The content of teaching English is a three-fold educational event: 1) topics of speech; 2) requirements for skills and qualifications; 3) language material. The teaching content is selected according to the available conditions, including the time allocated to the subject. Program topics determine the extent of verbal engagement.

The discourse created (speaking, writing) and performed by another person (listening comprehension and reading) is directly related to the topics covered by the program. The content of English language teaching is directly related to the teaching goals, which usually determines the content of the goal. If the content is a methodological concept or category to be mastered during education, then its product reflects the goal to be achieved.

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